

NEW UZBEKISTAN: STRATEGY FOR SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF TERRITORIES

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ANNOTATION. The article focuses on the theoretical issues of the regional economy, modern problems, ways to solve them, the priority directions of regional development, the need to abandon the practice of centralizing state administration, the need to continue the process of transfer of many powers from the central state bodies to regional bodies and other such topical issues.

Keywords: regional economy, regional policy, region, territory, potential, parameters of development, modernization, diversification, strategy, integration, specialization.

1. Introduction.

In Uzbekistan, entrepreneurship is developing and the economy is growing. Ultimately, the working mood of the population is rising, the quality of goods production, work performance and service provision is increasing, and their types are increasing. The parameters of socio-economic development of the regions for the medium and long term are defined and development strategies are being determined.

This process assumes a systematic continuation of reforms. The effectiveness of the measures being implemented puts the assessment in the cross-section of the territories on the agenda.

In turn, the failure to improve the mechanism of systematic monitoring of the timely adoption and implementation of targeted programs based on a clear assessment of the territory capabilities to further accelerate the pace of socio-economic development is creating certain problems.

Reform means renewal and change, a more thoughtful feeling of responsibility for the outcome of affairs. The positive result of the reforms is that the management system, our leaders and people must change. If a person's worldview changes, the society changes, renews, and thus the foundation of New Uzbekistan is strengthened.¹

Today, the study of the economic problems of the regions, the search for untapped reserves and their effective use are becoming more important than ever. In the strategy of New Uzbekistan in 2022-2026, serious attention was paid to the issues such as "...expanding the scale of modernization and diversification of the regional economy, reducing differences in the level of socio-economic development of regions due to rapid development of districts and cities with a relatively low level of development, first of all, by increasing the industrial and export potential"² based on the principle of Action Strategy – Development Strategy in seven priority areas of further development.

¹ Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Development strategy of New Uzbekistan. Completed second edition. -Tashkent: "Uzbekiston" publishing house, 2022. – 416 pages.

² Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Development strategy of New Uzbekistan. Completed second edition. -Tashkent: "Uzbekiston" publishing house, 2022. – 416 pages.

It is engaged in the study of current issues specific to the socio-economic development of territories, ecological-economic problems, the financial and credit system and its role in the innovative development of regions, the effective mechanisms of regional economic interaction and the development of regional strategies for economic development.

The most important factors of the economic development of territories include the optimal combination of diversification and specialization of the economy and the centralization of innovations in priority directions.

The following problems are considered within the scope of socio-economic development of territories: economy of individual regions; economic relations between them; regional systems (as a system of national economy-interacting regions); deployment of production forces; regional aspects of economic life; modeling of regional management systems; improvement of mechanisms and methods of management of economic activity in the region, etc.

By carrying out the policy of socio-economic development of territories, the state pays special attention to issues such as the uniqueness of regions, their socio-economic situation, their socio-economic development, issues of interregional integration, and support for problem regions, transferring some directions of reforms directly to the regions, reducing and eliminating serious differences between the socio-economic development of different regions and territories. In the strategy of New Uzbekistan, it is emphasized that it is necessary to abandon the practice of centralizing state administration, and to continue the process of transferring many powers from central state bodies to territorial bodies.

2. Literature review.

Socio-economic development of the territories began to take shape in the XIX century. Among foreign researchers, German economists – Johann Heinrich Tünen, Alfred Weber, Walter Kristaller, August Lesch, professor made the greatest contribution. Walter Isard from the Faculty of Economics of the University of Pennsylvania, French economist Jean Chardonne, Russian-American economist Vasiliy Leontiev, V.Thompson, T.Palander, as well as well-known textbook authors Kh.Armstrong and J.Taylor developed problems of regional economic theory, distribution of production forces and territorial production efficiency. The most vivid contours were shown in the works of Walter Isard, the founder of regional science, at the intersection of economic theory and economic geography in the USA in the 1950s. Among the Soviet researchers of the first half of the XX century, G.M.Krjijanovskiy, I.G.Alexandrova, V.V.Kuybisheva, N.N.Kolosovskiy dealt with the issues of long-term planning and economic zoning. Since the 60s of the twentieth century, regional economics has been the most fully developed in Russia, and it is interpreted as a branch of economics that studies the economic development of regions in order to plan the territorial organization of the economy. Among the local scientists of the second half of the twentieth century, the following should be noted: T.S.Khachaturova, Ya.G.Feygina, N.N.Nekrasov, A.G.Granberg, R.M.Alampiev, E.V.Alaeva, K.N.Bedrintseva, G.I.Granika, F.D.Zastavniy, R.S.Livshits, K.I.Klimenko, Yu.K.Kozlova, A.M.Korneeva, V.V.Kistanov, A.G.Omarovskiy, N.N.Oznobina, V.F.Pavlenko, M.M.Palamarchuk, Yu.G.Saushkina, E.D.Silaeva, N.I.Shrag and V.M.Torosov (*“Regional Economy” 2004 (“The best scientific book in Russia in 2004”)*).

The main task of the socio-economic development of the territories is to scientifically justify a reasonable compromise between the economic interests of the whole country and its individual territories.

The following problems are studied within the framework of socio-economic development of the territories:

- the economy of a certain region;
- economic relations between territories;
- regional systems (national economy as a system of interacting territories);
- deployment of productive forces;
- regional aspects of economic life;
- modeling of the territorial management system;
- improvement of mechanisms and methods of management and regulation of economic activity in the region³.

In his monograph “Regional Economy: Development Factors” (*St. Petersburg: Publishing House of St. Petersburg University of Management and Economics, 2014. -266 p. ISBN 978-5-94047-703-7*), O.G.Smeshko studied the factors determining the development of the economic space of the territories. Based on the analysis, the author based the principles of assessing the socio-economic condition of the territories, the formation of the theory of the economic development of the territory, as a means of adopting effective management, the solutions of the methodology of territorial management were proposed. The monograph is designed for employees of state bodies, authorities and local state authorities, scientists and employees of departments, issues of socio-economic development of territories⁴.

3. Research methodology.

The methodology of writing the article was defined as the task of introducing a rating system for socio-economic development of territories and it includes decrees, resolutions and works of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on state support, resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers, and works of local and foreign scientists on the problems of territorial development. In the research process, it is based on the wide use of methods such as economic statistics, economic-mathematical modeling, expert evaluation, statistical grouping, observation through questionnaires, monographic works and scientific observation.

4. Analysis and discussion of results.

Regional development or regional policy of the state should include the following goals: proportional socio-economic development of the regions of the country while ensuring the territorial integrity and integrity of the country; reducing regional disparities in people’s living standards and quality; creating equal opportunities for the population of the country to exercise their socio-economic rights, regardless of which territories they live in⁵.

Resolution of the President “On the introduction of the system for rating the socio-economic development of territories” allows to develop work in this field at a new level and to solve existing problems⁶.

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https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/%D0%A0%D0%B5%D0%B3%D0%B8%D0%BE%D0%BD%D0%B0%D0%BB%D1%8C%D0%BD%D0%B0%D1%8F_%D1%8D%D0%BA%D0%BE%D0%BD%D0%BE%D0%BC%D0%B8%D0%BA%D0%B0

⁴ https://www.spbume.ru/file/pages/76/smeshko_mon.pdf

⁵ Industrial management and its importance in sustainable economic development M.I.Kutbitdinova – Economics and Innovative Technologies, 2018

⁶ Resolution of the President “On the introduction of the system for rating the socio-economic development of territories” No. RP-4702 dated on May 1, 2020.

The task of introducing a system for rating the socio-economic development of territories has been determined, and the formation of the system will be based on statistical indicators and questionnaires. In this, special attention is paid to 8 main criteria and each direction is assessed.

The first – ensuring stable and balanced economic development in the territories and the effectiveness of economic reforms. Sufficient attention was paid to the proportionality of economic development in all territories, and this direction was set as the main criteria.

The second – creating new jobs in the territories, reducing unemployment and ensuring the efficiency of the labor market. In this regard, it is possible that the internal capabilities of the territories are not being used sufficiently. The specific characteristics of the territorial economy, that is, the directions of specialization, have different effects on the structure of the labor market and the effectiveness of this market. From this point of view, this process requires deep and systematic observations.

The third – increasing access to social services in the territories and improving the quality of life of the population. The quality of life of the population represents the final result of the reforms, that is, it is considered the main criterion of social well-being, and in-depth analysis of work in this regard is one of the main requirements.

The fourth – creating the necessary conditions for the population and business in the territories, ensuring the stability and reliability of the production infrastructure. Ensuring the economic activity of the population in the territories and creating the necessary conditions for the entrepreneurial activity of business circles often depends on the diligence, initiative, efficiency and skills of working closely with the population of local authorities. The stability of production is closely related to the availability of good infrastructure. In turn, the creation of necessary conditions for the population and business expands the possibility of rational use of labor, capital, mineral raw materials and other resources available in the territories. This criterion provides an opportunity to evaluate the conditions created for small business and private entrepreneurship activities of the population in the territories.

The fifth – increasing the level of competitiveness of the territories, further diversifying the economy. Territories in some sense compete with other territories in the national market, in turn, in the regional and international markets, these territories combine their opportunities and potential, they now become a single economic force and compete at the international level. Also, competitiveness depends on the production capacities available in the territories, and the level of industrialization of the territory. If the territories have a one-sided economy, then the level of competitiveness will be undermined. Diversification of the territorial economy directly increases the level of competitiveness, and this criterion is given special importance.

The sixth – improving the quality of the business environment in the territories, continuous support and rapid development of entrepreneurship. The territories have a wide range of opportunities for further development of public-private partnerships between business circles and local authorities, however, due to insufficient attention in places to the organizational, legal, institutional and social aspects of the business environment, the entrepreneurial layer cannot effectively use its potential. In addition, it is appropriate to approach the development of entrepreneurship on the basis of large, medium and small business levels, from the point of view of their integration. Entrepreneurship should become a constantly active and dynamic socio-economic force with great potential. Therefore, based on this criterion, it is possible to make a systematic assessment of the business environment of the territories.

The seventh – achieving financial independence of the territories and development of the banking and financial sector. Significant changes have been made in this regard in recent years. At the same time, there is a need to continue the reforms aimed at achieving financial independence of the territories. This is an important factor for local khokimiyats to conduct an active socio-economic policy in the territories. In turn, local budgets will expand the possibility of solving issues of freedom and transparency in the formation of revenues and distribution of its expenses. By developing the banking and financial sector, necessary conditions are created for further improvement of horizontal and vertical relations in the economic complex of the territories, therefore, the assessment of the situation in the territories according to this criterion will be an incentive to accelerate the reforms in the sector.

The eighth – improving the efficiency of working with citizen's appeals and the openness of information of local government bodies in the territories. Fundamental reforms in our country began with the adoption of the concept of administrative reforms. After that, the principle "State agencies should serve the people" has been gaining deep socio-economic content year after year. This criterion gives an opportunity to assess the extent to which this principle is more deeply applied to life in the territories.

In recent years, the issues of development of the economy of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Tashkent city and regions are being discussed in a systematic manner in individual, district and city sections. Now, rating indicators are formed at the level of districts and cities. This is very important. Because if the results of rating assessment are carried out not only at the level of regions, but also at the level of districts and cities, through these indicators, it is possible to assess the rate and scale of economic reforms in which territories, the contribution of the regions of our country to the increase of the overall socio-economic potential.

It serves to ensure the effectiveness of the socio-economic reforms implemented in the territories and to more effectively use the local internal opportunities to raise the standard of living of the population.⁷

5. Conclusion and suggestions.

In conclusion, it is necessary to take into account the problems specific to the territory when developing strategies for the medium and long term. In the strategy of New Uzbekistan, the territorial economy will be increased by 1,4-1,6 times through the proportional development of territories, and the five-year territorial programs will be implemented for 14 territories in terms of districts and cities, a program of practical measures will be developed for cities and districts with "unsatisfactory" socio-economic development rating indicators. In order to improve the living conditions of the population in the territories, further improvement of urbanization policies should be focused mainly on the implementation of measures to turn Samarkand and Namangan into promising "million cities", the construction and commissioning of the first few themes of the New Andijan city with a population of 450 thousand people. Bringing the level of urbanization of Kashkadarya region to 50%. Introduction of the "Comfort of Cities" index, which evaluates the comfort of the lifestyle of residents in cities. Digitization of cities, improvement of the quality of construction and design work and development in accordance with the concept of "Smart City". Organization of innovative educational and production "INNO" Technopark, established in the Tashkent city, in 4 territories. Mastering technologies for the production of innovative products

⁷ <https://uza.uz/uz/posts/ududlarni-izhtimoiy-i-tisodiy-rivozhlantirishni-ba-olash-tiz-12-05-2020>

that create high added value in districts that are being transformed into innovative territories. Combining scientific research with practice in the field of architecture and construction in higher education institutions. Technical regulation of the construction industry. Development and implementation of the program for the fundamental improvement of the system of development of urban planning documents of settlements and the provision of urban planning documents. Development of the master scheme of population settlement. On the basis of renovation and housing programs, the construction of more than 19 million square meters of modern housing instead of old houses in cities, and the creation of conditions for more than 275 thousand families to move to new massifs are defined in the strategy of New Uzbekistan.

Also, development of the engineering-communication and social infrastructure system of the territories, as well as service sector. Within the framework of the “Obod kishlok” and “Obod makhalla” programs, special attention should be paid to the construction of engineering, communication and social infrastructure facilities based on the “growth points” of the territories. Construction and renovation of nearly 80 thousand kilometers of main and distribution power lines, more than 20 thousand transformer points and more than 200 substations in the territories of the republic. Bringing the level of provision of drinking water to the population of the republic to 87%, upgrading wastewater systems in 32 large cities and 155 district centers. Introduction of modern technologies for remote sensing and repair of water leakage points in water supply pipelines using satellite technology. Development of new facilities in Tashkent city on the basis of Public-Private Partnership, bringing the sewage treatment system outside the territory of the city. Increasing the volume of services by 3 times in the next 5 years and creating a total of 3,5 million new jobs in this direction through the development of service sector in the territories. Development of paid plumbing, electricity, home appliance repair, and catering services for the development of household and communal services that are highly needed by the population in the centers of cities and districts. Establishment of 130 modern markets and shopping complexes, as well as 65 large and 5000 small service facilities for the development of roadside infrastructure through the development of trade and roadside services in the Republic territories. Reducing the share of the hidden economy in the service sector by 3 times. In order to increase the attractiveness of the service sector, it is appropriate to provide additional benefits to business entities in the sector⁸, and to pay attention to the main factors of the complex socio-economic development of territories.

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⁸ <https://www.sammu.uz/frontend/web/upload/content-files/61fb9c694a831.pdf>

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